

Storage and Compute Infrastructure Project

Project Title

High Throughput Computing in Australia: Applications, Tools and Services

Project Summary

This project investigated current and future demands for high throughput computing (HTC) tools and services in the research sector in Australia and how these services can be effectively supported. From a user perspective, the project aimed at identifying requirements of NCRIS capabilities and users for such capabilities. From a provider perspective, the project identified similar infrastructures overseas supporting HTC as well as the role commercial clouds can have in this space. This was achieved with a number of semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders, including users and providers of NCRIS facilities, researchers from Cooperative Research Centers (CRCs) and major research groups in Australia. The project has been complemented with interviews with managers and support staff of relevant international research facilities so that best practices can be recommended for Australian providers. From this work, we identified key themes that emerged across the user community including the need for higher level portal and management tools for interaction with the underlying infrastructure; the need for special purpose hardware such as GPUs; providing reusable microservices toolbox for domain-specific research platforms; and appetite for integration of research facilities with commercial clouds.

Project Goal

In this project, we investigated the current and future demands for high throughput computing (HTC) tools and services in the research sector in Australia and how these services can be effectively supported. To be more precise the following questions were answered:

- What are the requirements of NCRIS capabilities and major research groups for these types of services?
- What exemplars are there in Australia and internationally of these kinds of services?
 - Commercial cloud services, hybrid cloud, specialized hardware?
- What is the best approach for supporting these services on different infrastructures (including the Nectar Research Cloud) and how can we encompass hybrid cloud including local infrastructure (clusters, local cloud, etc.), and commercial cloud?
- How can we best take advantage of commercial cloud pricing options for these requirements?

Approach

We followed the approach outlined in our proposal. We started our project with in-home research using available documents and reports to explore the current demand of HTC applications and HTC tools and services used by the research sector in Australia, including NCRIS projects and major research groups. We also liaised with Intersect¹ as the project partner and a number of interviews were conducted with Intersect staff that provide support for researchers with HTC applications. During the interview, we aimed to identify recurrent user needs as experienced by Intersect staff, how these needs are supported and what issues are currently not addressed. Intersect also provided access to reports that show common trends in resource utilization by research groups, so we could identify patterns of activity, utilization, and idleness of resources allocated to researchers, which we analyzed as part of this project to provide insights into patterns of resource usage.

In the next stage, we conducted semi-structured interviews with researchers in Australia. Criteria for invitation was based on identification of application areas and research areas that match HTC applications, as self-reported by institutional data/web information. In this stage, we interviewed 20 research leaders and technical managers including CRCs, NCRIS projects, University-based research institutes (both in Australia and overseas), and research groups within CSIRO.

The final step consisted in obtaining insights into issues of resource infrastructure providers in Australia and overseas. Besides Intersect, we also contacted in this stage National Laboratory for Scientific Computing (LNCC) (Brazil), National Institute of Informatics (NII) (Japan), Grid'5000 (France) and XSEDE (US). The objective of this stage was to obtain insights about how HTC applications are supported overseas and identify potential best practices that could be adopted in Australia. Please refer to the supplementary report² for more discussions about this project.

Findings

In this section, we discuss the findings of the project that relate to the first two project goals (requirements and exemplars of HTC services). We also include in this section a short list of technical challenges faced by users of HTC applications in Australia while using national infrastructures.

HTC Application Requirements and Demands

From our interviews with researchers and users of HTC applications, a number of requirements were identified, which are briefly discussed below.

- **High level portal to access facilities and execute applications:** existing facilities are difficult to operate and require ICT domain knowledge from users, which in many cases are from other fields of science and engineering. Thus, easier ways to execute HTC applications are needed. Ideally, the underlying platform should as transparent as possible so scientists

¹ <https://intersect.org.au/>

² http://staff.scem.uws.edu.au/~bjavadi/download/ARDC_Project_WSU_Supplementary.pdf

can focus on their applications rather than operational issues. This interface should also offer services such as queueing and resource management, similarly to what is available in HPC clusters.

- **Dynamic resource allocation:** the current resource allocation on national infrastructures is mainly based on researcher requests or sometimes personal connections. This becomes an issue when research teams have allocations of several machines with low utilisation and no incentive to release them while there are other groups who need more resources, but they cannot obtain enough resources for their demands.
- **Specialized hardware:** There are a number of research groups that require GPUs to run specific HTC applications. These GPU-optimised codes are popularizing in the research community, so access to this specialized hardware is required.
- **System Interoperability:** This is an essential feature that, whenever a distributed facility is available, service availability and service versions are homogeneous across all sites, so users can utilize any node or eventually migrate their applications across nodes without needing to adapt their applications. Facilities should also interoperate with commercial cloud providers, so these external facilities can be used for cloud bursting (when local resources do not meet application demand) or when extra service level guarantees are needed.

Exemplar HTC Services

We identified exemplar overseas facilities that support HTC services, and interviewed key personnel to provide us insights on how these facilities are managed and what types of support they offer to users. Next, we discuss two of these cases, and finalize the section with a discussion on support from commercial cloud providers.

National Laboratory for Scientific Computing (LNCC – Brazil): although it is primarily a supercomputer facility providing HPC services, it also provides explicit support for users of HTC applications. The same level of instructions and scripts for HPC workloads is provided for HTC workloads. More important, these workloads leverage queues and resource management software, just like regular HPC workloads, providing a seamless experience for users regardless of their workloads. In order to support new researchers, LNCC offers regular workshops and hosts a research group that aims to improve resource utilization (for example, via performance tuning and efficient parallelization of applications), usually engaging with application groups in joint research and publications. LNCC does not integrate with public clouds, and such an integration is not on their plans. A few of the supercomputer nodes have GPUs as well.

National Institute of Informatics (NII – Japan): NII operates as an academic cloud that integrates with all major cloud providers, and thus provides an interesting case of support for hybrid clouds. They operate their own cloud data center, but also have a framework that enables easy integration with commercial cloud providers. They also have GPUs available for researchers. Like LNCC, NII also offers training for researchers to utilize their platforms. There is a data management system in place to help researchers to store, process and share their research data using high speed interconnection between academic cloud and national research facilities.

Commercial cloud providers: commercial public clouds also have some services that can facilitate execution of HTC applications. Of particular relevance, Amazon Web Services (AWS) has a service called AWS Elastic Beanstalk that enables a complete infrastructure for execution of a worker environment (which can be easily mapped to HTC applications). With a few clicks and the definition of few parameters, a complete infrastructure containing virtual machines, queueing

systems, and workers running on the VMs that fetch jobs from the queue is deployed. AWS also offers virtual machines with GPUs, so applications that require them can also be supported. Other provider's support for HTC applications is Microsoft Azure Batch, which can also build a cluster-like environment with minimum user input, thus being accessible for users with minimum ICT skills. Other relevant services from commercial clouds are discussed in the following sections.

Technical Challenges

While conducting this project, we identified a number of technical challenges faced by researchers using national infrastructures (mainly the Nectar Cloud) which is listed as follows:

- Low availability/reliability of national infrastructures compared to commercial clouds.
- Lack of support for integration with commercial clouds.
- Manual data transfer and lack of integrated data management systems.
- Difficulties in access control outside research communities.

Analysis and Emerging Themes

Given the requirements of various research groups as well as the current challenges to utilize the national infrastructures for HTC applications, we can recommend the following solutions to address the last two project goals:

- **Hybrid Cloud:** Most research organizations and universities in Australia have their own computing systems and integrating these systems to the Research Clouds could make the existing infrastructure more agile and flexible to run HTC applications. The same platform can also be used for seamless integration of Research Clouds with commercial clouds to extend the provided services for HTC applications. Example of this service is Platform9 which is offered by Intersect.
- **Automatic management tools:** Many research teams in Australia use open source applications for their scientific research and run these applications on national infrastructures. Having an automatic management tools will help researchers to easily create a batch processing environment to configure dynamic number of resources, manage job queues and schedule HTC workloads. This can improve the resource efficiency as well as help researchers to focus more on analysing results and solving scientific problems. Example of this service in commercial clouds is Microsoft Azure Batch, which is designed for scalable batch processing.
- **Elastic deployment tools:** For researchers who want to develop their own applications and increase the productivity in development and deployment, an elastic deployment tools can be recommended. Having a simple and fast way to develop and deploy HTC applications can help researchers to focus on their applications rather spending time managing and configuring servers, storage and health monitoring. Example of this service in commercial clouds is AWS Elastic Beanstalk, which is designed for web and batch applications.
- **Reusable microservice toolbox:** Several teams around Australia are building their own software ecosystems and developing a number of microservices to address requirements of researchers from various disciplines. Providing a centralised reusable microservice toolbox on national infrastructures will help researchers to reuse existing services and improve the efficiency, productivity and collaboration of the research groups. Example of this service is developed as part of Science Cloud project in Australia (e.g., ecoCloud).
- **Idle resource usage:** One of the observed issues in national infrastructures in Australia is low resource utilisation due to inefficient resource management (see the supplementary

report). One possible solution is to provide a new service to run low priority HTC applications on idle resources. This service harvests idle time on national infrastructures and provides extra flexibility to run HTC applications. These applications should be able to tolerate interruptions due to resource preemption using restart or checkpointing mechanisms. Example of this service is provided by Grid'5000 to send low priority jobs to a 'best effort' queue to be executed while the servers are idle.

- **Specialised services:** Since there are a number of HTC applications that need to access sensitive data such as medical dataset, it is recommended to provide dedicated hosts on Research Clouds for such applications for better isolation and security. Example of such service is AWS Dedicated Host, which is provided with higher prices to customers. In addition, some HTC applications can utilise specialised hardware such as GPUs, which is recommended to be added as part of national infrastructures.
- **Serverless computing:** Functions as a Service (FaaS) is a new paradigm in cloud computing to provide computing services with less focus on servers. Providing this service on national infrastructures will help researchers to focus only on code development and increase resource efficiency. While current serverless platforms have several limitations including short running time and stateless applications, it will be one of future directions to provide computing services. AWS Lambda and Google Functions are example of such service in commercial cloud providers.

While the aforementioned services and recommendation can help to improve the support for HTC applications on national infrastructures, researchers could possibly utilize available commercial cloud services to meet the requirements of their applications. Since the monetary cost is the main hurdle to use these services, considering cost optimize is essential. We provided some of the available pricing options which can be utilized by researchers on commercial clouds:

- **Reserved Resources:** Given that research organisations are able to have an ongoing plan for their research programs, it is possible to use reserved resource discounted pricing from commercial cloud providers. In this case, they could reserve a certain amount of resources for a specific period of time and receive a substantial discount on resource costs, which makes these services quite affordable. Examples are AWS Reserved Instances, Google Committed Use Discounts, Azure Reserved Instances and IBM Reserved Virtual Servers, which provide a contract of 1 or 3 years with about 70%-80% discount of their prices.
- **Discounted Resources:** Many commercial clouds offer discounted resources as a way to monetize their excess capacity. The price of these resources could vary with the supply and demand, but significantly cheaper than normal prices. These resources can be used to run HTC applications with very low prices. Amazon Spot Instances, Azure Low-Priority VM, Google Preemptible Instances and IBM Transient Servers are example of such service with average price saving up to 90%.
- **Research Credits:** Most commercial cloud providers have research support programs where they offer free resources to researchers around the world on a merit-based process. This can be leveraged for development of new applications or some of the new scientific projects. Example of this service is AWS Cloud Credits for Research and Google Research Credit.

Issues and Barriers to Goals

Our semi-structured interviews method was suited well the objectives of the project, and enabled us to identify issues and develop the recommendations presented in the previous section. The team did not meet any unforeseen issue that hindered the project execution.

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ARDC Discovery Activity: Storage and Compute Infrastructure Project (Supplementary Report)

High Throughput Computing in Australia: Applications, Tools and Services

Executive Summary

In this project, we investigated current and future demands for high throughput computing (HTC) tools and services in the research sector in Australia and how these services can be effectively supported.

To be more precise the following questions from the call for applications were addressed:

- What are the requirements of NCRIS capabilities and major research groups for these types of services?
- What exemplars are there in Australia and internationally of these kinds of services?
 - Commercial cloud services, hybrid cloud, specialised hardware?
- What is the best approach for supporting these services on different infrastructures (including the Nectar Research Cloud) and how can we encompass hybrid cloud including local infrastructure (clusters, local cloud, etc), and commercial cloud?
- How can we best take advantage of commercial cloud pricing options for these requirements?

This report complements the official report submitted to ARDC by giving more insights in the concept of HTC applications, typical scenarios, and some exemplar applications from Australian researchers.

Project Partner

Intersect¹ was the supporting partner for this project. Intersect is the Australia's largest full-service eResearch support agency. They provide robust, innovative services and collaborative technology to support world-class research for member organizations and the Australian research community. Intersect delivers expert advice, compute and analysis platforms, data storage, custom engineering, consulting and training programs to thousands of researchers every year. Intersect helps researchers increase their impact through innovative technologies and expert advice.

What is High Throughput Computing?

The European Grid Infrastructure defines High Throughput Computing (HTC) as “A computing paradigm that focuses on the efficient execution of a large number of loosely-coupled tasks. Given the minimal parallel communication requirements, the tasks can be executed on clusters or physically distributed resources using grid technologies”². In contrast, High Performance Computing (HPC) tends to focus on tightly coupled parallel jobs, and as

¹ Intersect: <https://intersect.org.au/>

² https://wiki.eui.eu/wiki/Glossary_V1#High_Throughput_Computing

that could be provided as a small text file or as command line parameters). However, each task can take hours to complete depending on the complexity of the model being executed.

Other Considerations

The scenarios above discuss general trends of HTC applications. However, variations to the model also exist, which affect the way scheduling solutions and resource needs is affected. For example:

- In some situations, the application can have a massive number of tasks (hundreds or thousands) that are not necessarily compute-intensive. However, there is still a need to manage scheduling, execution, and failures of these small computing tasks.
- Some applications can be *memory intensive* in that they require large amounts of memory not always available in computers. In this case, more powerful resources are needed to support these tasks. Furthermore, this type of task limit exploitation of multicores, as one task alone is likely to demand most of the available memory.

HTC Applications and Tools in Australia

We have conducted a number of interviews with several research groups in Australia to identify the applications and tools in HTC as briefly listed in the following:

Genomics: A genomics application we identified in this project is a black-box application, meaning that the research team was not aware of how the application is implemented. However, characteristics that emerged is that tasks did not benefit from extra memory, but executed faster when more cores were available, indicating some type of multithreaded code. As such, it is functionally equivalent to finite element applications described above and thus can be managed by having tasks being submitted to nodes for execution. If some nodes have more available cores, some of the tasks would be accelerated, contributing to a higher task throughput.

Image processing: This is one of the “textbook” cases for HTC, ad common among scientists in Australia. In this application, the objective is performing some operation such as analysis, filters, or modifications in images provided as input. Sizes of these images can vary, and so can the computational complexity of a single application. Some of these images, for example, deriving from telescopes, can have considerable size and require considerable amount of processing, whereas other cases may require small computations in a huge number of inputs.

Statistical analysis: A number of research groups have applications that can be describe as execution of some type of analytics in the data, usually with the help of software such as R, Matlab or Python libraries. Although the particular domain of the application varies, they usually well-defined statistical and machine learning methods, and can involve steps of model training before analysis. In most of the methods, usually the training step is more resource-intensive, but occurs with much less frequency than actual inference.

EEG analysis: EEG³ analysis is another HTC application we identified in the Australian research community. EEG analysis is independent for each participant data being analyzed. They are characterized by high I/O demand (each single participant, which translates to one task, can have up to 10GB). Thus, when a high number of tasks are going to be execute, a

³ Electroencephalogram

strategy for data transfer needs to be in place, otherwise, the data transfer time can dominate the time to complete all the required analyses.

Simulations: A number of applications we identified are simulations in diverse domains, and their structure are similar to our Scenario 2 above. Although the particular method for simulation (such as Monte Carlo, finite element, or discrete event) determines the particular computational demands of a single simulation (task), in conceptual level they can be described as a single class of application: there is a number of input *parameters*, and the objective of the computation is to analyze the effects of various combinations of these parameters in the environment being simulated. The parameter space can grow quickly if a single parameter has many values to be tested. Some simulation methods (such as Monte Carlo) usually can run as a single core application, and thus more computing cores enable more combinations of parameters (a task) to run in parallel. Finite element simulations are more common in the HPC domain, because each single simulation can utilize many cores that need to exchange data during computation. However, for small and medium sized problems, each simulation can occupy a single node and leverage all the cores of the node, enabling HTC to be used to map tasks to nodes. Discrete-event simulations can either run as a single core application, or can be implemented as distributed discrete event simulations, where many cores or nodes support the execution of a single task. In the latter, the same considerations than finite element simulations apply.

Exemplar HTC Services

We identified exemplar national and overseas facilities that support HTC services and reported a number of them which could be helpful to give us insights on how these facilities are managed and what types of support they offer to users. We provided two examples from Brazil and Japan in the main report. We included national services and other two examples from US and France in the following:

National Infrastructures (Australia)

Nectar Research Cloud: The National eResearch Collaboration Tools and Resources project (Nectar) provides Infrastructure as a Service for Australian researchers. It includes sites in all Australian capital cities (currently six nodes). Services including compute (virtual machines and containers), storage (volumes and block storage), database, and ancillary services (networking, security, images). It also supports analytical jobs based on Open Source frameworks such as Hive, MapReduce, Pig, Storm, and Spark. Internally, it is based on OpenStack, a cloud middleware that resembles the cloud organization, services, and APIs from Amazon Web Services. The frameworks supported for job execution are not compatible among themselves, and they implement different programming paradigms. This means that utilization of these frameworks is not trivial and the knowledge on one does not translate easily to use others. Furthermore, control of the underlying cluster that executes the jobs is delegate to end-users.

NCI Cloud: The National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) operates the Canberra node of the Nectar Cloud. It also operates the Tenjin cloud, which is a cloud service that interoperates with the NCI HPC cluster. The specification of Tenjin nodes resembles typical specification of HPC cluster nodes rather than clouds. Another similarity with HPC facilities is the use of high-performance networking that uses efficient drivers to bypass the host system and deliver network packages directly to virtual machines. More important, Tenjin can access the storage

and filesystem of the NCI HPC cluster using the optimized network, making it a good candidate for data-intensive jobs. In common with Nectar, the cloud is managed with OpenStack.

Pawsey Cloud: The Pawsey Supercomputing centre is in Western Australia. Like NCI, it also provides HPC and cloud services, but this time on the Western Coast of Australia. Its OpenStack-based cloud service, called Nimbus, also mirrors other features of NCI, such as integration with the HPC storage system. It offers a few GPU nodes that can accelerate applications that can leverage such specialized hardware. Interestingly, Pawsey supercomputer documentation provides scripts for execution of parallel jobs in the supercomputer. This means that HTC users can leverage these scripts to submit their HTC tasks to the HPC cluster in a much higher level of abstraction than if they wanted to perform the same task in the cloud (as described in the main report, LNCC in Brazil exhibits the same feature regarding scripts for execution of HTC applications in a HPC cluster).

XSEDE (US)

The Extreme Science and Engineering Discovery Environment (XSEDE)⁴ is a single virtual system that US scientists can use to interactively share computing resources, data and expertise. The XSEDE ecosystem encompasses a broad portfolio of resources operated by members of the XSEDE Service Provider Forum. These resources include multi-core and many-core high-performance computing (HPC) systems, distributed high-throughput computing (HTC) environments, visualization and data analysis systems, large-memory systems, data storage, and cloud systems⁵. Researchers requiring large amounts of computing power for tightly coupled MPI, OpenMP, and hybrid programs can use XSEDE-allocated high-performance computing (HPC) resources. In addition, for massively parallel jobs that require far less communication and synchronization, researchers can consider high-throughput computing (HTC) options. This help researchers to have a single interface to manage and execute their applications and reduce their learning curve.

Grid'5000 (France)

Grid'5000⁶ is a French national research infrastructure which provides a large-scale and flexible testbed for experiment-driven research in all areas of computer science, with a focus on parallel and distributed computing including Cloud, HPC and Big Data. It is distributed around the county with 8 sites and more than 14000 cores and 150 GPUs.

Experiments performed on Grid'5000 typically require several resources reservations which are handled by the OAR⁷ resource manager. Resources can be reserved using three different queues (*default*, *production*, *besteffort*), with different usage policies. Unless specified otherwise, jobs are submitted in the default queue. It is possible to reserve resources as soon as possible (submissions, typically for small-scale reservations) or using advance reservations (for larger-scale experiments, during nights and weekends). Providing a single interface helps users to submit their jobs and execute and monitor them easily.

⁴ <https://www.xsede.org/>

⁵ <https://www.xsede.org/ecosystem/resources>

⁶ <https://www.grid5000.fr>

⁷ <http://oar.imag.fr/>

The *besteffort* queue provides a way to submit low-priority, interruptible jobs. This is how this system takes advantage of idle servers in the system to improve the resource efficiency and provides HTC services to researchers.

Resource Usage Analysis

We have conducted a resource usage analysis based on information provided by Intersect from the utilization of Intersect SpaceTime Research Cloud Computing Service⁸ (including the Nectar Research Cloud) from one of their academic partners. Fig.2. shows the resource allocations versus resource usage for cores and memory in these infrastructures for duration of 18 months. As can be seen in these figures, there are long durations of time that idle resources are up to 40%, which reduces significantly the resource efficiency and in long term the overall research productivity as other teams are no able to use these resources.

Fig.2. Sample resource usage from national infrastructures (data from Intersect)

In order to address this issue, we recommend a number of solutions that can be used for resource management in national infrastructures. Having automatic management tools will help researchers to create a dynamic resource pool and have more efficient resource allocation. In addition, having new tools to explore idle resources and allocate them to low priority HTC applications can improve the resource utilization further.

Commercial Clouds for HTC Applications

While national infrastructures are improving their services and supports, researchers could possibly utilize available commercial cloud services to meet the requirements of their HTC applications. Since the monetary cost is the main hurdle to use these services, considering cost optimization is essential. Many commercial clouds offer discounted resources as a way to monetize their excess capacity. The price of these resources could vary with supply and demand, but it is still expected to be significantly cheaper than normal prices. Some cloud providers also have fixed pricing for these resources to make it easier for users to predict the usage cost. These resources can be used to run HTC applications with very low prices. These applications should be able to tolerate interruption due to resource preemption using restart or checkpointing mechanisms. AWS Spot Instances, Azure Low-Priority VM, Google Preemptible Instances and IBM Transient Servers are example of such service with average price saving up to 90%. Fig. 3 summarizes the main features of these services offered by the four major cloud providers.

⁸ <https://intersect.org.au/cloudtime/>

Features/ Cloud	IBM Cloud			
Service Name	EC2 Spot Instances	Low Priority VMs	Preemptible VMs	Transient Servers
Pricing	Variable	Fixed	Fixed	Fixed
Shutdown Lead Time	2 Mins	30 Secs	30 Secs	None
Maximum Time Limit	None (depends on extra capacity)	None (depends on extra capacity)	24 Hour Limit and certain instances within 6 hours	None (depends on extra capacity)
Capacity Management	Spot Fleet	No	Instance Groups	No
Cost Visibility	Spot Instance Advisor	Fixed Pricing	Fixed Pricing	Fixed Pricing

Fig.3. Summary of discounted resources in four major commercial cloud providers (Source: spotinst.com⁹)

Edge Computing for HTC Applications

Edge computing is an emerging computing model that combines cloud data centers with computing devices closer to where data is generated (usually from Internet of Things devices). Research that analyzes data generated by sensors are emerging in a number of areas in Science. As this type of research disseminates, the capability of conducting some processing closer to researchers, while delegating to the cloud more challenging computations, will become more important. Providers of facilities can also benefit from this capability: if more of the data is processed closer to researchers, network and processing capabilities at the provider will be reduced, enabling more customers to be served with the same amount of resources. Thus, infrastructure providers should keep a closer look on how the demand of data analysis from sensors among the research community grow in the next years, and should be prepared to invest in Edge computing as a way of relieving their data centers.

⁹ <https://spotinst.com/blog/amazon-ec2-spot-vs-azure-lpvm-vs-google-pvms-vs-ibm-transient-servers/>

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